

Appendix

Table 2. The AI Deployment Management Capabilities (AI-DMC) and the descriptive review of the executive interviews.

AI-DMC	Shares of companies (out of 8) representing the items descriptive for each DMC.		
<i>Understanding the role of AI in digitalization and strategy (1-4)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 3/8 considers AI as a tool and has value (only) as an instrument. * 4/8 fears competition will by-pass if not start deploying AI. * 4/8 has AI applications in production and 1/8 has systematically deployed AI for years. * 6/8 does not have AI connected to company strategy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 6/8 see that AI is “coming”. * 5/8 think AI enables value creation and company development. * 4/8 don’t know when is “the right time” to start utilizing AI. * 2/8 sees connection to strategy through IT or technology strategy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 8/8 understand the importance of data and its refinement. * 3/8 are piloting AI. * 2/8 are not interested in AI (or do not understand it). * 2/8 sees the connection to company strategy through “doing”, i.e. AI will be used in the strategic projects.
<i>Working the roadmap to deployment (5-6)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 8/8 see in their vision that use of AI will increase in the next few years. * For 2/8 the focus in company strategy is customers. * For 7/8 the goal is to make operations more efficient. * 3/8 use AI in marketing * 3/8 use AI in processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 3/8 wonder what is possible with AI (no vision yet) * For another 2/8 the focus is sustainability. * 2/8 sees the main use in forecasting. * 2/8 use AI in legal function 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 1/8 says that IT-function use AI, but it is not used in business. * For 3/8 the focus is profitable growth. * 2/8 see the main use of AI in analytics. * 3/8 mention single functions
<i>Setting the building blocks for business goals and results (7-10)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 3/8 set project-based objectives for AI deployment. * 4/8 follows AI projects using business metrics (like costs, gained benefits) * 4/8 say we develop AI with our own resources. * 2/8 say they have digitalization budget (including AI) beyond 10M€ * 7/8 mention some business target (like predictive maintenance) as a gained result * 5/8 expect to gain or have realized efficiency benefits * 2/8 expect to gain or have realized customer satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 2/8 set KPI’s for the biggest AI projects * 2/8 no metrics set yet * 1/8 says all the strategic applications are developed and deployed in-house. * 2/8 say that investment level in AI is 1-3m€ * 2/8 mention quality management as gained result * 2/8 mention efficiency boosting as gained result * 2/8 expect to gain or have realized quality improvements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The remaining 5/8 do not set deployment objectives so far. * 1/8 says that AI investments not discussed yet in board * 4/8 say we use partners to develop the AI applications. * 3/8 say that AI is included in IT-budget * 1/8 expects to retain credibility or visibility in markets, achieve time savings, increase in vocational safety, decrease manual work or improve cash flow (separate answers) * 2/8 do not know or do not have results yet
<i>Solidifying the bedrock for continuous learning and development (11-13)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 2/8 sense the urgency and are deploying AI actively as early adopters. * 2 /8 perceives AI as a management challenge, not a technical one. * 3/8: see data availability as an enabler * Several separate mentions for needed capabilities such as personnel age, attitude, technology curiosity, amount of robust proprietary data, businesses’ AI understanding, level of skills using AI, learning capability. * For 2/8 obstacle is lack of (skilled) labor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 1/8 recognize themselves as followers. * 2/8 see own organization as an enabler (young people, structure) * For 1/8 obstacle is that AI takes time and costs a lot 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 2/8 keep asking themselves whether they are “doing enough”. * 1/8 say (separate mentions) university cooperation, companywide closed environment for data, own people, process owners, funding as an enabler * 1/8: no obstacles seen

*2/8 sees an obstacle that **AI is not taken seriously** (or others win the market)
* For 2/8 **TMT does not understand** or does not know what to do is an obstacle

* 6/8 share the following **data challenges**: data ownership, (vast) amount of data, data availability, lack of common data platform, data siloed in organization units

* 5/8 the share **learnings** that new skills are needed, although it is not necessarily clear yet what is needed

* 1/8: attitudes of the personnel esp. in **trade union** is an obstacle

* 3/8 lack of AI-skillful personnel is a **challenge**

* 2/8: **scalability** of solutions

* 3/8: when and how to start, "we are **facing the unknown**"

*3/8: change of **mindset and understanding** needed in TMT

All other **learnings** are separate mentions like:

* 1/8 AI is not as simple as thought

* 1/8 we are able to increase the efficiency and quality

* 1/8 we need to understand the issue or the opportunity

* 1/8 these are not technical issues but related to leadership

*1/8 security issues is a **challenge**

*1/8 productivity

*1/8 lack of resources

Ensuring strategic leadership for endurance and differentiation (14-16)

* 2/8 of executives **are on the map on AI** and its meaning.

* 5/8: AI is important, AI increases efficiency

* 3/8: **without AI competitors are winning** the game, it is a question of existence

* 3/8 do **not recognize** or understand AI and its meaning.

* 2/8 say AI is very important, we **invest a lot**

* 3/8: In AI we are still at early stages, but **it will grow** much bigger

* 2/8 is **not a game changer** in our business

*1/8 considers AI as "IT functions job".

* 1/8 it is an **ecosystem game**, you need to orchestrate the actors

* 1/8 **customer demand** is decisive

* 1/8 it will **ease labor shortages**